

COMPETITIVE PRESSURE AND CUSTOMER

SATISFACTION: BOON OR BANE

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ABSTRACT

The impacts of competitive pressure and customer satisfaction have been studied. Also its effects on business sector have been studied with the help of an example.

Keywords: *Bane, Boon, Competitive Pressure, Customer satisfaction, Industry*

I. INTRODUCTION

Competitive pressure means the pressure felt by an organisation or individual in the environment as a result of competition. Competitive pressure is an external force resulting from behaviour of members of community, the firm that interact dynamically with its competitor, regulator imposing rules of conduct, customer wishing for better quality and better price and so on. Day by day, the competition is rising among different firms or organisation, due to which the firms have lots of pressure to sustain their firm in the competitive world. The 21st century is full of competition, the reason behind this, is establishment of large number of firms or companies of the same product.

Customer satisfaction refers to the extent to which customers are happy and satisfied with the products and services provided by a business. Customer satisfaction is important because when a customer is happy with a service or goods provides, they are likely to be loyal and to make repeat orders and to use a wide range of services offered by a business. This will boost business sales.

“Customer satisfaction is the key aim is selling process”

If we are going for the banking sector, there are lots of players like ICICI, AXIS, and HDFC etc. To lead in the competitive world they have to provide best service at best cost, so that the customer gets attracted towards their services.

II. REASONS FOR COMPETITIVE PRESSURE

Competitive pressure arises mainly because of the following reasons (shown in Fig 1 also):

2.1 Bargaining power of supplier:

The term “suppliers” comprises all sources for inputs that are needed in order to provide goods or services.

Supplier bargaining power is likely to be high when,

- 1) The market is dominated by a few large suppliers rather than a fragmented source of supply.
- 2) There are no substitutes for the particular input.
- 3) The suppliers, customers are fragmented, so their bargaining power is low.

2.1 Bargaining Power of Customers

It determines how much customers can impose pressure on margins and volumes. Customer bargaining power is likely to be high when,

- 1) They buy large volumes; there is a concentration of buyers.
- 2) The supplying industry comprises a large number of small operators.
- 3) Customer could produce the product themselves.
- 4) The customer knows the production costs of the product.

2.2 Threat of New Entrants

The competition in an industry will be the higher, the easier it is for other companies to enter this industry. In such a situation, new entrants could change major determinants of the market environment (e.g. market shares, prices, customer, and loyalty) at any time. There is always a latent pressure for reaction and adjustment for existing players in the industry.

The threat of new entries will depend on the extent to which there are barriers to entry. These are typically-

- 1) High initial investment cost.
- 2) Brand loyalty of customer.
- 3) Scarcity of important resources, e.g. qualified expert staff.
- 4) Access to raw material is controlled by existing players.
- 5) Existing players have close customer relations, e.g. from long-term service contracts.

2.3 Threat of substitute

It exists if there are alternative products with lower prices or better performance parameters for the same purpose. They could potentially attract a significant proportion of market volume and hence reduce the potential sales volume for existing players.

The threat of substitutes is determined by factors like,

- 1) Brand loyalty of customers.
- 2) Close customer relationship.
- 3) The relative price for performance of substitutes.

2.4 Competitive Rivalry Between Existing Players

This force describes the intensity of competition between existing players in an industry. High competitive pressure results in pressure on prices, margins and hence on profitability for every single company in the industry.

Competition between existing players is likely to be high in the following cases:

- 1) There are many players of about the same size.
- 2) Players have similar strategies.
- 3) There is not much differentiation between players and their products; hence there is much price competition.

Fig1. Reasons for the Competitive Pressure

III. REASONS FOR CUSTOMER SATISFACTION

Customer satisfaction arises mainly because of the following reasons (shown in Fig2 also):

3.1 Customer Focus

The orientation of an organisation towards serving the need of its clients. Having a customer focus is usually a strong contributor to the overall success of a business and involves ensuring that all aspects of the company put its customer's satisfaction first. Also having a customer focus usually includes maintaining an effective customer relations and service program.

3.2 Special Requirement of Customer

In addition to our regular products, request for special products are received. It is the endeavour of the company to see that special characteristics are built into the products, to satisfy requirement of the customer.

Some of the special requests are as follows:

- 1) Size of end committees.
- 2) Special packaging requirement.
- 3) Special colours of paints used etc.

3.3 Customer Grievances

As with the business, certain grievances would also be arising. Prompt action is taken to remove any irritants so that grievances are reduced at the first place. Main grievances that the unit gets are:

- 1) Supply of materials at short notice period in the season. We do inform the customers, the minimum time required to supply the materials.
- 2) Quality related problems are very few and the reasons are-
- 3) Quality raw materials are used.
- 4) Proper processes are adopted at different stages of manufacture etc.

3.4 Customer Feedback

As a part of ISO-9001-2000 system, the company collects feedback from the customers at regular intervals. Such feedbacks are by various methods, viz,

- 1) By sending a standard format & collecting the data.
- 2) From our marketing personnel, while they interact with customers during tours.
- 3) As and when the customers visit the unit.

3.5 Customer Property

Customer property is any property that is owned (or provided) by the customer. In simple terms, customer property can be considered anything that you don't own, that has been supplied by the customer for your use.

Example of customers' property can be found in ISO-9004-2000 which includes the following-

- 1) Ingredients or components supplied for inclusion in a product.
- 2) Product supplied for repair, maintenance or upgrading.
- 3) Packaging material supplied directly by the customer.
- 4) Customer materials handled by service organisations such as storage.

3.6 Timely supply: To satisfy our customers, we have to supply the products on time so that they don't have to face problems with their needs.

- 1) Timely supply plays an important role to satisfy our customers.
- 2) In 21st century nobody have lots of time to wait for the products. In that case they can give their orders to other firms. In this way, lacking in timely supply we can diminish our sales rate.

Fig2. Reasons for Customer Satisfaction

IV. COMPETITIVE PRESSURE AND CUSTOMER SATISFACTION

Following points give the reasons in the support of the above question:

- 1) Competitive pressure accelerates the growth of the firm or organisation indirectly. Due to competitive pressure, the firm is always active to produce the good & quality product to satisfy the customers. Due to it, the firm always try to give their best to the public, so that they can withstand with the other firm. In the 21st century, there is a lot of competition, for a single product, many firm, companies are ready to produce.
- 2) Existence of large number of firms increases the competitive pressure.
- 3) The general consumer gets the big advantage, because they are getting the quality & best product at a lower cost. So if customers are satisfied with the product, then definitely they will purchase more and more. In this way, it will become the boon for the firm or the organisation.
- 4) Due to competitive pressure, the owner of the firm or organisation also makes pressure to the employees of the firm. Sometimes, this pressure makes the employees to take some unwanted decisions like suicide, resign, etc. At that time it will become bane for the firm.
- 5) Competitive pressure increases the frustration among the employees.
- 6) Customer satisfaction always works as a boon because if customers have been satisfied by any firms or organisation, the image of firms or organisation would be increased.

V. EXAMPLE

The following example is to elaborate the study on competitive pressure and customer satisfaction. We are taking the example of banking sector. By going through this example we can easily understand the changes happening in the expenditure and income/profit of banks due to competitive pressure in the market. For this we are taking 13 old private banks and 7 new private banks. We have taken data from website “www.iba.org” of Indian banks association for analysis.

Here O is operating expenses and I is Interest expended

Table 1. Old Private Sector Banks

Row Labels	Sum of 2013(i)	Sum of 2013(o)
City Union Bank Ltd.	1564.7397	374.1997
Dhanlaxmi Bank Ltd	1031.5765	339.3213
ING Vysya Bank Ltd.	3322.9537	1272.8161
Nainital Bank Ltd.	246.1043	80.0621
RBL Bank	621.7734	227.2961
Tamilnad Mercantile Bank Ltd.	1610.8423	418.5299
The Catholic Syrian Bank Ltd.	981.6479	331.8202
The Federal Bank Ltd.	4192.9123	1184.5389
The Jammu & Kashmir Bank Ltd.	3820.757	989.0151
The Karnataka Bank Ltd.	2860.5563	666.0358
The Karur Vysya Bank Ltd.	3083.9621	762.197
The Lakshmi Vilas Bank Ltd.	1368.5498	337.9177
The South Indian Bank Ltd.	3153.4644	767.1686
Grand Total	27859.8397	7750.9185

Row Labels	Sum of 2014(i)	Sum of 2014(o)
City Union Bank Ltd.	1786.5435	479.6145
Dhanlaxmi Bank Ltd	1011.827	347.4885
ING Vysya Bank Ltd.	3452.066	1492.7336
Nainital Bank Ltd.	268.7234	92.9496
RBL Bank	1009.9892	423.9032
Tamilnad Mercantile Bank Ltd.	1820.4817	489.2626
The Catholic Syrian Bank Ltd.	1124.7734	401.1983
The Federal Bank Ltd.	4717.466	1442.0708
The Jammu & Kashmir Bank Ltd.	4082.5162	1174.9926
The Karnataka Bank Ltd.	3132.761	874.601
The Karur Vysya Bank Ltd.	3832.2568	1010.3616
The Lakshmi Vilas Bank Ltd.	1497.9395	395.0054
The South Indian Bank Ltd.	3616.2948	882.8913
Grand Total	31353.6385	9507.073

Table2

Row Labels	Sum of 2012(t)	Sum of 2013(t)	Sum of 2014(t)
City Union Bank Ltd.	1476.8552	1938.9394	2266.158
Dhanlaxmi Bank Ltd	1635.0947	1370.8978	1359.3155
ING Vysya Bank Ltd.	3758.6658	4595.7698	4944.7996
Nainital Bank Ltd.	273.351	326.1664	361.673
RBL Bank	417.3879	849.0695	1433.8924
Tamilnad Mercantile Bank Ltd.	1581.0601	2029.3722	2309.7443
The Catholic Syrian Bank Ltd.	1067.3744	1313.4681	1525.9717
The Federal Bank Ltd.	4584.2582	5377.4512	6159.5368
The Jammu & Kashmir Bank Ltd.	3799.3743	4809.7721	5257.5088
The Karnataka Bank Ltd.	2937.0598	3526.5921	4007.362
The Karur Vysya Bank Ltd.	2894.8099	3846.1591	4842.6184
The Lakshmi Vilas Bank Ltd.	1441.7434	1706.4675	1892.9449
The South Indian Bank Ltd.	3178.9778	3920.633	4499.1861
Grand Total	29046.0125	35610.7582	40860.7115

Table 3

Row Labels	Sum of 2012(i)	Sum of 2012(o)
Axis Bank Ltd.	13976.9024	6007.0995
Development Credit Bank Ltd.	489.2683	244.2527
HDFC Bank Ltd.	14989.578	9277
ICICI Bank Ltd.	22808.4964	7850.4433
Indusind Bank Ltd.	3654.9484	1342.9956
Kotak Mahindra Bank Ltd.	3667.746	1834.8299
YES Bank	4691.7212	932.5343
Grand Total	64278.6607	27489.1553

Table4. New Private Sector Banks

Row Labels	Sum of 2013(i)	Sum of 2013(o)
Axis Bank Ltd.	17516.3111	6914.2375
Development Credit Bank Ltd.	631.6946	275.2948
HDFC Bank Ltd.	19253.7521	11236.1165
ICICI Bank Ltd.	26209.1848	9012.8837
Indusind Bank Ltd.	4750.3662	1756.3627
Kotak Mahindra Bank Ltd.	4836.8183	2209.731
YES Bank	6075.2092	1334.5367
Grand Total	79273.3363	32739.1629

Table 5

Row Labels	Sum of 2014(i)	Sum of 2014(o)
Axis Bank Ltd.	18689.522	7900.7739
Development Credit Bank Ltd.	759.8696	319.0863
HDFC Bank Ltd.	22652.8999	12042.1981
ICICI Bank Ltd.	27702.5886	10308.8614
Indusind Bank Ltd.	5362.8213	2185.2828
Kotak Mahindra Bank Ltd.	5047.0665	2542.6072
YES Bank	7265.0918	1749.8719
Grand Total	87479.8597	37048.6816

Table 6

Table 7

Table 8. Old Private Sector Banks

Table 9. New Private Sector Banks

The following are some findings after observing the data:

- 1) Table 1 and 2 shows the operating expenses and interest expenses of old private sector banks separately. So that we can understand them clearly. These are shown by the graphs also.

- 2) Table 3 shows that the total expenditure is increasing continuously from previous year where the total expenditure $t = \text{Total expenditure (interest expenses + operating expenses)}$. The total expenditure of 2013 is greater than 2012 and the total expenditure of 2014 is greater than 2013. We can see it from the chart also.
- 3) Table 4, 5 and 6 shows that expenses of new private sector banks in the year 2012, 2013 and 2014 respectively.
- 4) Table 7 explains the total expenditure (interest expenses + operating expenses) during year 2012, 2013 & 2014.

Now we are going to see the effect of competitive pressure on the profit of the 13 old private sector banks and 7 new private sector banks. How it affect the profit of both old and new banks.

- 1) Table 8 explains the total profit of 13 old sectors private banks of consecutive year 2012, 2013 & 2014. This table shows that the net profit of 13 old private sector banks are increasing first then decreasing in the next year compare to previous year. It shows the effect of competitive pressure on the banks. The net profit decreases because of pressure among banks.
- 2) Table 9 explains the total/net profit of 7 new private sector banks of year 2012, 2013 & 2014. We can see the net profit of old private sector banks are increasing. This table explains that competitive pressure has a positive effect on the new comers/new firms. Due to competitive pressure, the new firms lead as compared to the old firms or the existing firms.

The following tables show that “competitive pressure and customer satisfaction” is boon for new banks and bane for old banks.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this competitive world, everyone has to be sincere to develop and to maintain its firm's image. In business sectors, companies are facing lots of pressure due to switching of customers and also this switching causes a significant impact on their firm's performance. In this paper, we have showed with the help of an example of banking sector that old private banks' performance are far behind the new private banks' performance because customer are very well satisfied with new private banks. In this example, we found that new private banks' net

profits was increased due to switching and increase in number of customers. So we can conclude that competitive pressure is a boon for new private sector banks and bane for the old ones or the existing ones.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Emin Babakus and Ugur Yavas, Does sex influence the relationship between perceived quality and share of wallet?, *Journal of Business Research*, 61, 2008, 974-981.
- [2]. T. Bresnahan, Empirical studies of industries with market power, In: *Handbook of Industrial Organization*, 2, 1011- 1057, Elsevier Science, New York: 1989.
- [3]. Priyaranjan Dash and Suryakanta Mishra, Developing RFM Model For Customer Segmentation In Retail Industry, *International Journal of Marketing & Human Resource Management (IJMHRM)*, 1(1), 2010, 58 – 69.
- [4]. C.Fornell, M. Johnson, E. Anderson, J. Cha and B. Bryant, The American Customer Satisfaction Index: Nature, purpose, and findings, *Journal of Marketing*, 60, 1996, 7-18.
- [5]. .G. Gaddamwar and P.R. Rajput, A Review on Privatization In Education Is The Boon For Percentages of Educated, and Bane For Quality, Unemployment, *International Journal of Mechanical Engineering & Technology (IJMET)*, 4(4), 2013, 373 – 376.
- [6]. Philip Kotler and Kevin Keller, *Marketing Management* (Prentice Hall, 2006).
- [7]. J. E. Post, L. E. Preston and S. Sachs, Managing the extended enterprise: The new stakeholder view. *California Management Review*, 45, 2002, 6-28.
- [8]. K. Venkateswara Raju, S. Srinivasa Raju and D. Prasanna Kumar, Benefits of FDI In Indian Retail Sector and Customer Perception of Organized Retail Outlets In Hyderabad, *International Journal of Management (IJM)*, 4(4), 2013, 180 – 192.
- [9]. R.T. Rust, A.J. Zahorik, and T. L. Keiningham, Return on quality (ROQ): Making service quality financially accountable, *Journal of Marketing*, 59, 1995, 58-70.
- [10]. S. H. Sawant, Customer Satisfaction and Loyalty In After Sale Service, *International Journal of Management (IJM)*, 4(4), 2013, 180 - 192,.
- [11]. S.B. Akash, Opportunities and Challenges of Retailing Business in India- An exploratory study, *KAIM, Journal of Management and Research*, 2, 2009, 37-44,.
- [12]. Vijay. R. Kulkarni , A Study of Impact of Music on Customer Buying Behavior In Retail, *International Journal of Management (IJM)*, 3(3), 2012, 152 - 159.
- [13]. G. Young, K.G. Smith, and C. Grimm, Austrian and industrial organization perspectives on firm-level competitive activity and performance, *Organization Science*, 7, 1996, 243-254.